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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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ACUTE NEPHROTOXICITY OF DOXORUBICIN - COMPARATION OF ANIMAL MODELS

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Introduction: Doxorubicin (DOX) is an effective anticancer drug with many adverse effects. We aimed to compare commonly used doses for the acute model of doxorubicin-induced toxicity on animal's general condition, body weight and kidney morphology.

Materials and methods: Animals were randomly assigned to groups C (n=10, 1ml saline), M1 (n=10, 15mg/kg DOX) and M2 (n=10, 20mg/kg DOX). Kidney tissue was subjected to standard histological processing, staining and qualitative analysis. The body weight was measured before treatment and before sacrificing. As signs of animal's general condition, we observed: quality and density of the hair and bleeding.

Results: Compared to C and M1, the M2 group had higher mortality and worse general condition (thinned fur of significantly worse quality, traces of bleeding from the nose and gastrointestinal tract). During necropsy of M2 animals, the presence of serohemorrhagic content and coagulum in the chest were observed. Kidney tissue morphology was

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altered compared to the control. The changes in the M1 model were milder and affected fewer nephrons (mild/moderate hypercellularity and slight decrease in the number and size of the renal corpuscles, hyperemia, rare vacuolization of the proximal tubules). In M2, nephrotoxicity was more pronounced and widespread, affecting all zones of the cortex and medulla of the kidney (hypercellularity and atrophy are moderate/pronounced, vacuolization is present in majority of proximal tubules). In addition to previous, in M2 distal tubules are dilated, with desquamated and partially karyopyknotic epithelium and intraluminal calcifications occasionally, numerous areas of hemorrhage were present in cortex.

Conclusions: Nephrotoxicity was dose-dependent, which may be linked to a direct toxic effect on the nephron. In order to induce histopathological evidence of nephrotoxicity, both doses can be used, but considering that a high dose leads to a worse general condition and higher mortality, lower doses are recommended.

Keywords: doxorubicin, nephrotoxicity, animal models